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Review Article

Living With Albinism in India Shades of White in a Brown Nation

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ABSTRACT

Albinism is a rare genetic condition characterized by the lack of melanin, which affects the hair, skin and eyes. In a country like India where brown skin tones predominate. Living with albinism often carries not only medical challenges but also deep social stigma. Individuals with albinism struggle with poor eyesight, extreme sensitivity to sunlight, premature skin damage and in some cases, they need to dye their hair to blend into society. Beyond the medical issues they face discrimination, isolation and misconceptions rooted in cultural myths. The articles aim to raise awareness about the realities of albinism in India. It highlights the importance of genetic counselling and screening to understand the probability of passing albinism to children, thereby helping families make informed choices. At the same time, it stresses the urgent need for government support, including free annual checkups with ophthalmologists and dermatologists as well as subsidies for protective care such as sunscreen and visual aids.

INTRODUCTION

Albinism is an autosomal recessive disorder characterized by hypopigmentation of the skin, hair and eyes. Due to the absence or severe reduction of melanin biosynthesis Clinical

manifestations include ophthalmic complications like photo phobia, nystagmus, reduced visual acuity and cutaneous problems such as hypopigmented skin, high sensitivity to sunlight and increased risk of skin cancers

Types of Albinism

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India oculocutaneous albinism is the most common type. In the OCA2 is mostly seen in Indian populations. Ocular albinism is not common here and systemic. Albinism is rare but documented. Estimated number of people with albinism are 100000 -200000 There is no national registry or complete census data in India specially counting people with albinism. OCA is a group of inherited disorders characterized by reduced or lack of melanin pigment due to defects in the gene responsible for melanin production

Melanin:

Melanin is a natural pigment that gives color to skin, hair and eyes It is produced inside special cells called melanocytes through melanosomes

Types of melanin

- Eumelanin: black or brown pigment
- Pheomelanin: red and yellow pigment

Melanogenesis

Role of melanin:

- Determination of skin, hair and eye color
- Skin protection from U.V radiation
- Free radical scavenging
- Thermoregulation
- Vision protection

Lack of pigment:

- Vision problems
- Skin disorders
- Sun sensitivity
- U.V Damage and skin cancers
- Prone to sunburn

Genes involved in melanogenesis:

Gene	Effect of mutation	Type of OCA
TYR	Complete absence of melanin	OCA1A
		OCA1B
P Gene	Reduced melanin	OCA2

TYRP1	Reddish brown skin/hair	OCA3
SLC45A2	Reduced melanin similar to OCA2	OCA4
Other rare gene	Variable pigment reduction	OCA5 -OCA7

Genetic basis of albinism and importance of screening:

OCA is an inherited autosomal recessive pattern, Mean, a person must inherit a mutated gene from both parents

The following section illustrates four genetic inheritance cases of albinism

1. An individual with albinism marrying normal [non-carrier] person
2. Two carrier parents
3. One carrier parent and one normal parent
4. Both parents with albinism

Each case shows the probability of their children being affected, carrier or unaffected

Case 1

Affected (aa) x Normal (AA) → 100% Carriers (Aa)

In this case, an individual with albinism [aa] marries a normal person with no mutated gene [AA]. since all offspring receive one normal allele [A] from the healthy parent and one mutated allele [a] from the affected [parent, **100% of children**

became carriers [Aa] . They do not show albinism symptoms but can pass the gene to the next generation.

Case 2

Carrier (Aa) x Normal (AA) → 50% Normal (AA), 50% Carriers (Aa)

When a carrier marries a normal individual [AA], each child has 50% chance of being normal [AA] and 50% chance of being a carrier [Aa] none of the

children will have albinism, but half may carry the gene and pass it to future generations

Case 3

Carrier (Aa) x Carrier (Aa) → 25% Affected, 50% Carriers (Aa), 25% Normal (AA)

When both parents are carriers [Aa + Aa], there is a 25% chance the child will be affected [aa] a 50% chance of being carrier [Aa] and a 25% chance of being completely normal [AA]. This combination

shows the typical autosomal recessive inheritance pattern of albinism

Case 4

**Affected (aa) x Affected (aa) →
100% Affected (aa)**

When both parents carry [aa+aa] affected genes there is a **100% chance the children will affect [aa]** the inheritance now depends on whom the children marry like a person with affected gene, normal or carrier gene

Screening can be performed through **genetic testing, carrier testing, or prenatal diagnosis**. in addition to early diagnosis and management, screening plays a crucial role in **genetic counselling, prevention of recurrence and psychological support for affected families**

Importance of screening:

Genetic screening for albinism is very important to identify individuals who carry or express the gene mutation. Early screening helps determine whether a person is affected, a carrier or genetically normal

Many individuals carry one mutated gene for albinism without showing any visible symptoms these people are called carriers screening helps detect such hidden carries, especially in families with known or suspect history of albinism. identifying carriers allows for preventive measures and informed family planning. Before marriage genetic screening is strongly recommended to ensure that a carrier does not marry another carrier, this enables couples to choose partners wisely reducing the risk of transmitting the condition

Physical challenges faced by albinos:

1. Extreme sun sensitivity

- Intense U.V radiation in topical climate of India causes frequent sunburns and increases the risk of skin cancers

2. Hair dyeing [in India]

- Many individuals dye their hair to match social norms in India, but the chemicals can irritate the scalp and increase the cancer risk

3. Visual impairments

- Common problems include photophobia, reduced vision, and nystagmus, making

outdoor visibility and classroom learning difficult

4. **High risk of skin cancer**

- Due to lack of pigmentation and high sun exposure, albinos in India especially are prone to developing skin cancers early in life

5. **Social stigma and discrimination**

- Misconceptions and lack of awareness lead to teasing bullying and social exclusion in schools and workplaces

6. **Educational barriers**

- Most individuals with albinism experience reduced visual acuity making it difficult to read printed texts and boards in classrooms in bright light
- During stressful situations rapid involuntary eye movement [Nystagmus] may intensify causing blurring
- These vision related problems can lower confidence

Health and psychological care for individuals with albinism in India:

People with albinism are born unique -their difference is not a weakness but a mark of rarity and beauty. In India where sunlight and social misconceptions often pose extra challenges, proper selfcare and self confidence can help albinos live healthy, fulling lives. Understanding how to take care of the skin, eyes, hair while developing emotional strength is the key to leading a confident life

Self-care tips

- **Protect your skin from sun exposure:**

Always apply a broad-spectrum sunscreen with SPF 30 or above before going outdoors. Wear full-sleeved clothing, hats or use umbrellas or scarves to protect yourself from harmful U.V rays

- **Regular dermatological checkups:**

Visit a dermatologist once every 6-12 months to monitor for sun damage, skin infections or early signs of skin cancer

- **Care for sensitive eyes:**

Wear sunglasses with U.V protection when outdoors and shaded lenses indoors if light sensitivity is high, sit away from direct sunlight in classrooms

- **Choose supportive visual aids:**

Magnifiers, high contrast reading materials albinos students should encouraged to sit in first rows during classes

- **Hair and scalp care**

Use mild, sulphate free shampoos and avoid chemical dyes

- **Balanced nutrition**

Eat foods rich in vitamins A, C and E to maintain eye and skin health

- **Community awareness:**

Participate in awareness programs and educate others about albinism to reduce stigma and discrimination when people learn the facts, fear and prejudice begin to fade

Prevention strategies for albinism

Genetic counselling:

Couples with a history of albinism should undergo genetic counselling before marriage helps them understand inheritance pattern, carrier status, and possible outcomes of their children

Carrier screening:

Genetic tests can detect whether individuals carry the mutated gene responsible for albinism

Prenatal diagnosis:

For couples known to be carriers, prenatal diagnostic tests such as amniocentesis or chorionic villus sampling can detect whether the fetus has albinism.

Public awareness program:

Educating communities about the genetic nature of albinism helps reduce stigma and encourages families to seek proper genetic evidence before planning children, especially in areas where consanguineous marriages are common

Government and NGO support for people with albinism in India

People with albinism often face financial and accessibility challenges in managing their dermatological and ophthalmology needs. Regular skin and eye checkups are essential for early detection of sun damage skin cancer and vision impairment however due to lack of awareness and affordability, many individuals are unable to necessary care. The government and NGOs can play a vital role in supporting them through dedicated health schemes, awareness programs, and social inclusion initiatives.

To support them the government and NGOs should organize annual free health checkups focusing on skin and eyecare, and provide subsidized specialist consultation under public

health schemes like Ayushman Bharath ,distribution of free or low cost sunscreens U.V protective sunglasses and hats through primary health centers can greatly help in sun protection .awareness programs are needed to educate families on regular medical visits , introducing special health cards , for people with albinism can ensure priority access and cost reduction at government hospital. Collaboration with NGOs and government agencies can strengthen community outreach, while individuals with severe impairment due to albinism under disability benefits, would help them access educational, employment, and travel concessions. Together these initiatives can improve both health and social inclusion for people with albinism

CONCLUSION:

Addressing albinism in India requires a dual focus on social change and systemic support. We must aggressively combat the ingrained social stigma discrimination through public awareness campaigns while simultaneously pushing for urgent government support that includes mandated free health checkups and subsidies for essential protective aids

The importance of protective genetic screening and counselling cannot be overstated. Empowering families with the knowledge to understand the probability of passing on albinism is crucial for making informed choices, thereby transforming the management of genetic condition from a passive burden into a supported family health choice

The future for people with albinism in India depends on our collective will to remove from cultural neglect to comprehensive care, ensuring their visibility is one of acceptance not vulnerability

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